

SMART CITY VALUATION AND LIFE CYCLE COSTING

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ABSTRACT

Smart cities combine ubiquitous computing and urban management, and are characterised by pervasive wireless networks and distributed sensor platforms from video surveillance to meteorological stations, monitoring flows from traffic to sewerage and providing information in real-time or in anticipation of risks. These have extended from small projects for example, shopping / business complexes with integrated building control systems combining video surveillance, fire detection and crowd flow monitoring.